

Article

Admission Control in Home Energy Management Systems Using Theatre and Hybrid Actors

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Abstract: The goal of a Home Energy Management System (HEMS) is that of purposely shaping the cumulative energy consumption curves of domestic appliances by imposing suitable monitoring and control policies. The development of HEMS, like the development of general Cyber-Physical Systems (CPSs), is challenging, as it requires the exploitation of suitable methodological approaches which are able to deal jointly with the continuous and discrete behaviours of a CPS. In this paper, a methodological approach for HEMS is advocated which relies on the use of the Theatre actor system with hybrid actors. As a key feature, Theatre enables the same actor model to be used during the analysis, design, prototyping and implementation phases of the system. For property assessment, a Theatre model is reduced to UPPAAL hybrid timed automata for analysis by statistical model checking. As a significant modelling example, a HEMS is proposed which implements an admission control strategy able to maintain the in-home energy consumption under a given threshold. Instead of reacting to an overload condition, the strategy is able to prevent an overload upfront by predicting the effect that the admission of a new load will have on the consumption curve of the whole system.

Keywords: cyber-physical systems; energy management; hybrid actors; model continuity; statistical model checking; UPPAAL

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1. Introduction

Nowadays, there are many research efforts addressing issues tied to the production, distribution and consumption of electrical energy. Many such efforts are directed to make energy utilization as efficient as possible, so as to promote environmental and economic sustainability [1–4]. The cost-reduction of IoT-based smart appliances and their pervasive diffusion favours the exploitation of efficient energy management strategies also in a domestic context [3,4]. A Home Energy Management System (HEMS) [3,5] is a Cyber-Physical System (CPS) for monitoring and management of in-home appliances with the goal of shaping the overall energy consumption curve by imposing a proper load scheduling policy.

Load scheduling is a multifaceted problem [3,4,6–8]. In a case, the goal could be that of promoting the reduction of energy consumption by the automatic scheduling of loads and by also providing feedback to customers for encouraging a more efficient use of electricity [8]. Comfort issues are considered in [7]. The performance of some scheduling algorithms is studied in [3] and the demand in terms of computational resources and the complexity of the required execution infrastructure are considered for assessing the performance. The automatic identification of plugged appliances is the goal of the work described in [9]. Privacy concerns in managing consumption profiles of the users are instead considered in [4].

While designing and implementing a HEMS, some important issues need to be taken into account. Some of them, tied to the development of CPSs in general, are: (i) guaranteeing a right coupling between the discrete dynamics of the cyber-part of the system with the

continuous behaviour (i.e., the *modes* of the system) of the physical environment in which the CPS operates. For these purposes, approaches and methodologies related to hybrid systems need to be used; (ii) assessing functional and timing properties of the system; (iii) adopting a development process that helps to transfer the validity of the analysed properties into the final system implementation; (iv) handling concurrency problems carefully.

Despite their importance, though, the above issues are often not adequately supported in today's computing and networking infrastructures, and no widely-used programming languages are capable of natively dealing with temporal properties [10].

In this paper, the Theatre infrastructure [11] enriched with *hybrid actors* [12] is advocated since they offer a modelling and development approach suited to cope with the problems so far discussed. A theatre is the runtime environment for actors. An *actor* is a software component (agent) which shares no data and communicates with other actors by exchanging asynchronous messages. Actors support a *cooperative* model of concurrency that simplifies the development of distributed/concurrent applications and avoid coping with common pitfalls of multi-threaded programming [13]. They are smart agents [14] having the ability to migrate dynamically from a computing node to another, thus possibly moving an intelligent behaviour close to the devices they have to interact with.

Hybrid actors naturally exhibit a time-dependent behaviour, and rely on the use of *continuous modes* thus permitting to model the dynamic behaviours of a CPS. Theatre and actors favour *model continuity* [15,16], that is the possibility of transitioning an actor model throughout the whole life-cycle of a system, from analysis down-to design, implementation and real execution. Property assessment is achieved by mapping a hybrid Theatre model onto hybrid timed automata for statistical model checking [17] in the context of the popular UPPAAL toolbox [18].

The contribution of this work is threefold: (i) the definition of an approach capable of revealing some desired/undesired properties emerging when coupling the cyber with the physical part of a CPS; (ii) the use of Theatre with hybrid actors in the case *what-if* scenarios are required to be evaluated and continuous behaviours require to be suspended and (subsequently) resumed; (iii) the exploitation of the approach in a significant modelling example related to the context of home energy management.

With respect to previous authors' works [19,20], this paper proposes a load scheduling strategy for HEMS relying on a prediction-based admission control policy [5]. More in particular, instead of reacting to an overload condition, the strategy prevents an overload upfront by predicting the effects that the admission of a new load will have on the consumption curve of the whole HEMS. Consumption curves, both real and predicted, of the considered appliances are specified by Ordinary Differential Equations (ODEs).

The structure of the paper is as follows. Section 2 summarizes some related works; Section 3 describes the HEMS chosen as a case study; Section 4 describes basic concepts concerning an actor-based design of CPSs and the use of the UPPAAL timed automata for modelling and analysis purposes; Section 5 details the achieved model for the HEMS; Section 6 shows some experimental results related to property checking; finally, Section 7 concludes the paper and gives some indications about on-going and future work.

2. Related Work

This paper proposes an original approach here used for modelling and analysing home energy management systems which is based on the use of time-sensitive actors in the context of the Theatre architecture and framework [11,12]. Actors [21] are highly-modular, concurrent and distributed software entities. They share no data and communicate with each other by asynchronous message passing. The Actor model born as a formalism well-suited to the development of untimed applications tolerating non-determinism in the message processing. Some variants of actors, though, have been proposed with the goal of addressing real-time constraints and enabling, in some cases, repeatability in the model execution by enforcing an ordered message delivery.

In [22], the proposed actor model relies on *reactors* which favour system composability by interconnecting typed input/output ports carrying events (messages). The behaviour of reactors is specified by *reactions*, which are message handler methods that can modify local data status and act as input/output event transformers. Timing aspects are managed through *timers* triggering reactions at selected times, and by *delays* and *deadlines* in reactors, which, respectively, constrain the generation of an output event or specify a time limit on the delivery of an event. Reactors rest on time-stamped messages. Reactors are part of the current meta-modelling polyglot language named Lingua Franca [23], which permits to specify the reactions' body in various languages like C, Python, and Java.

Other timed actor-based modelling and implementation languages, like Timed Rebeca [24] and Theatre [14], also rely on concepts borrowed from Reactors. In Timed Rebeca, an actor (rebec) owns an internal thread. Two attributes, namely *after* and *deadline*, can be attached to messages so as to specify, respectively, the time which has to pass before the message can be consigned, and the maximum allowed amount of time within which the message should be delivered. A message is discarded in the case its deadline expires. Timed Rebeca exploits a suspensive execution model for reactions (called message servers), in which a *delay* statement can be used to specify the duration of a code fragment. A model defined in Lingua Franca can be transformed into Timed Rebeca [23] for model checking by using the Afra tool. Theatre (see Section 4) syntactically resembles Timed Rebeca. However, a Theatre model (i) is composed of lightweight actors (they have no internal thread); (ii) actors have message reactions with non-suspensive semantics; and (iii) message scheduling and ordered delivery is regulated by a customizable control strategy. The possibility of exhaustive model checking CPS models based on a deterministic version of Theatre, when arbitrary continuous behaviour in peripheral entities is relaxed, is shown in [25].

Due to the ever-increasing demand for electric energy and to the availability of renewable power sources near to the utilization site (like photovoltaic panels and wind turbines), a great interest has grown in optimizing energy consumption also in domestic smart environments [9]. A HEMS is devoted to shaping the consumption curves of intelligent appliances, e.g., through the use of smart plugs, so as to impose suitable scheduling strategies with the goal of keeping the desirable overall power consumption under a given threshold.

Devising effective scheduling algorithms for electric loads is a multifaceted and challenging problem [3,4,6–8]. In many cases, a trade-off between energy consumption and the comfort level of the occupants is required to be considered. In [7], an adaptive algorithm devoted to reducing energy consumption without degrading the comfort level perceived by the home occupants is proposed. Deep Reinforcement Learning is used in [8] for on-line load scheduling optimization in a smart grid context. Here, in order to favour a more efficient use of electricity, the scheduling algorithm also provides the customer with some feedback in real-time. The use of different centralized and decentralized scheduling algorithms is instead provided in [3]. The main goal is that of helping customers in modifying their consumption patterns. Furthermore, the above paper compares some scheduling algorithms on the basis of the amount of needed resources and the complexity of the required runtime infrastructure. The work presented in [9] discusses a different issue that is tied to the automatic identification of an electric load after it is plugged into the energy management system. The minimization of the electricity bill is fostered in [26], where renewable energy sources are taken into account within a load scheduling strategy based on reinforcement learning. A Q-learning based approach for optimizing energy consumption which also admits variable consumers' habits and a variable energy price is proposed in [27]. The approach does not consider variable profiles for load consumption and self-produced energy. The problem of preserving privacy while managing people profiles is instead taken into account in [4].

The actor-based approach proposed in this paper is powerful and flexible, allows a formal modelling of an energy management system like scheduling appliances in a smart

home so as to reduce the electricity costs, and enables a thorough evaluation of model properties before transitioning the model to final synthesis and implementation.

3. A Home Energy Management System

A HEMS is a CPS devoted to automatically monitoring and managing the operations of in-home appliances. The goal is to enforce control policies able to shape the overall power/energy consumption curves [3,5,16,28,29]. For this purpose, many different techniques can be purposely used. For instance, a load shedding/shifting approach can be exploited in the case the total power consumption exceeds a given threshold [3,29].

The HEMS here proposed adopts an admission control policy on incoming loads which detects and prevents overload upfront [5]. Specifically, the proposed control policy is able to avoid that the admission of a new load could cause, in the future, the exceeding of a given consumption threshold. The approach, though, is more general and can be used, e.g., to ensure that the overall consumption curve of the system will own some specific features and properties without resorting to recovery operations.

Proposed approach permits to deal with a general challenge arising when developing CPSs which is to establish a proper *sampling frequency* for sensing the physical environments. This is an important precondition in order to properly couple the cyber and the physical part of the system. According to the well-known *sampling theorem*, the sampling frequency determines “the view” that the cyber component has of the physical one. Obviously, down-sampling the environment leads to a partial, yet distorted, vision of the physical world. Over-sampling the environment, instead, can be useless and resource-wasting. From a practical point-of-view it is important to choose the right (minimum) sampling frequency that permits the CPS to properly behave, and to determine how the system behaves when such frequency varies.

The chosen HEMS consists of a set of remote controllable smart plugs, a controller, and an energy meter. The meter is used to sample the actual consumption curves of the loads and to provide such information to the controller. By varying the frequency with which the meter sends a sample to the controller, it is possible to change the view that the controller has about the whole system.

Appliances can be dynamically plugged or removed, and the controller is used to determine if an incoming new load can be really activated or it must be deferred. A load is activated if its power consumption curve summed to the cumulative consumption curves of the already active loads will keep the future total requested power under a given threshold. In order to check this property, each load is able to furnish a prediction about its remaining/future power demand. As soon as a new load announces itself, the controller switches the HEMS into a *prediction mode* in which each load stops its execution and starts to furnish its future predicted power consumption. After the prediction phase, the controller will switch-back the system into the normal *operational mode* and will activate the incoming load only in the case that the threshold is not violated during the prediction. In the case where a violation emerges, the not-admissible load is added to a *deferred-load* set and, after a given timeout, the controller will again try to admit one of the loads in the waiting set by again checking violations on the threshold through prediction. Both in the *operational* and *prediction* modes, all the appliances evolve according to their known continuous behaviours, which are modelled through ODEs. The challenge here is that of: (i) suddenly freezing the evolution of all the continuous behaviours tied to the operating components as soon as a new load announce itself; (ii) evaluating how the system would evolve if the new load is added to the already operating loads and checking for threshold violations; (iii) restarting all the frozen continuous behaviour by resuming them from the exact point they were suspended and, if no violations occurred, making operating the new load.

The architecture of the considered HEMS is depicted in Figure 1. The system is made of two main parts: the cyber part, whose components implement the application logic of the HEMS, and the physical part whose components are place holders of the real equip-

ment. The cyber part contains the *Controller*, the *EMeter*, the *LoadManager* and four load components, namely, *EHairDryer*, *EHVAC*, *EWashingMachine*, and *EBoiler*, which manage the components in the physical part. The prefix *E* means *enhanced*. This is because such components enhance the functionalities of the managed real equipment by adding the prediction abilities required by the controller. The *LoadManager* is in charge of configuring and starting the system. The *EnvGateway* [16], is a boundary element permitting a transparent interaction between the cyber and the physical part. When the HEMS moves from the analysis to the implementation phase, the components into the physical part are replaced by real hardware components and only the *EnvGateway* will be affected by this change, all the other cyber components remain unaware of this phase transition. Communication patterns existing among components are highlighted in Figure 1 by using mono-directional and bidirectional arrows.

Figure 1. The architecture of the considered HEMS.

The consumption curves of the enhanced loads are reported in Figure 2. The red part of a curve represents the real power consumption. The light-blue part, instead, represents the consumption during the prediction phase. The curves are modelled and obtained by using *continuous modes*. Each load has its own specific continuous modes. To prevent visualization clutter, the prediction curves are purposely drawn by considering negative values. As a consequence, a prediction and a real curve of a given load will have the same shape but opposite sign. It is the responsibility of an enhanced load to furnish the proper kind of consumption curve on the base of its working state. Three working states are admitted, namely:

- *Active*: The load is operating and consumes real power. In this state, the time of the load evolves as the load performs its operation.
- *Coasting Forward*: The load is not operating and the time of the load gets frozen, i.e., it does not evolve. This phase is preparatory to the prediction state. Since the evolution of the consumption curves during prediction must start from the exact instant in which the load stopped to be active, a coasting forward phase is required to ensure that the prediction curve, starting from the beginning, reaches this instant. In the case a load was not yet activated, during the coasting forward, no operations are carried out.
- *Prediction*: The load is not operating but the time of the load evolves according to a virtual time notion exploited only for prediction purposes. Once started, the prediction phase runs to completion.

Figure 2. (a–d) The consumption curve (in KW) of the considered appliances vs. time.

From the above description, it follows that in Figure 2 two time notions are exploited on the x-axis of each consumption curve: a virtual time notion for the prediction and an operating time notion representing the evolution of the activities carried out by the load.

The controller regulates the state transitions of the loads and enforces that all the loads stay in “coherent states”. For instance, considering the scenario in which all the admitted loads are *Active*, on receiving an admission request from a new load, the controller suspends the active loads by turning them into *Coasting Forward*. As soon as all the loads completed the coasting forward, the controller switches the loads into *Prediction* and starts to monitor the predicted power in order to evaluate threshold violations. At the end of the prediction phase, the previously-suspended loads are turned again into *Active* and their operations are resumed. The new load is switched to *Active* if and only if no threshold violations occurred during prediction, otherwise the admission of the new load is deferred by the controller. This approach permits any load to be suspended and resumed whenever it is needed, and a new load can announce itself at any time.

The above-described components coordinate with each other by exploiting a purposely designed message interface. The messages exchanged in the system are reported in Table 1. For each message, the message name, a description, and the components using it are specified.

Table 1. Messages managed by the actors' templates of UPPAAL .

Message Type	Sender	Receiver	Description
INIT	Load Manager	ELoad	Setting-up load parameters
ON	Load Manager	ELoad	Switch-on a load. After switched-on, the load sends a REQUEST message to the controller
REQUEST	ELoad	Controller	Used by a load to ask the controller to become active
ACTIVATE	Controller	ELoad	Activates and makes operating a load. A previously active load resumes its operation from the point it was suspended last. An active load consumes real power
COASTINGF	Controller	ELoad	Suspends load activity (if any) and prepares the load to predict its remaining power consumption
READYTOPREDICT	ELoad	Controller	Communicates to the controller that the coasting forward phase is completed and that the load is ready to simulate its remaining power consumption
	Load Mode	ELoad	Used to communicate that the current mode completed the coasting forward
PREDICT	Controller	ELoad	Communicates that a load can start the prediction phase
PREDICTIONEND	Load Mode	ELoad	Used to communicate that the current mode completed its simulation phase
	ELoad	Controller	Used to communicate that a load completed its simulation phase
TERMINATED	ELoad	Controlled	Used to communicate that a load completed its task
SAMPLE	Load Mode	ELoad	Used to communicate that the current mode completed its behaviour
POWER	Meter	Controller	Communicates the instantaneous cumulative power consumption, both predicted and real, of the loads

4. Modelling Using Actors and Uppaal

The Theatre actor-based modelling language [11,30] and Java software framework [25] are chosen in this work for the development of time-critical cyber-physical systems [16]. The following summarizes the fundamental concepts of Theatre.

4.1. Basic Issues of Theatre

A Theatre is a federation of computing nodes (theatres/JVMs), connected to each other by network services (e.g., based on TCP sockets). A theatre hosts a collection of actors together with a transparent and customizable reflective control layer, i.e., the *control machine*, having the responsibility of regulating the scheduling and dispatching of messages. An actor is a modular entity encapsulating a data status. Communication among actors relies on asynchronous message passing. Differently from classical actor systems [21,24], Theatre actors are without threads. An actor is at rest until a message arrives. Message processing is atomic and cannot be suspended nor pre-empted. Actors do not have a local message mailbox, they depend on the buffering and time management services offered by the local control machine. The various control machines coordinate with each other in a distributed fashion so as to keep aligned, through the mediation of a *time server* [16], a notion of global time (real-time or simulated-time). The *macro-step semantics* [31] holds within a same theatre: the dispatch of each message runs to completion before a further message gets selected and dispatched. By default, the time needed for message processing is assumed to be negligible. In this way, a cooperative form of concurrency is obtained in a theatre by message interleaving, thus favouring time-predictability. True parallelism occurs among actors allocated on distinct theatres.

A Theatre model [11] can be abstracted by a set of *processing units* (PUs/theatres) and the actors can be allocated to PUs by means of the *move(act,pu)* operation. An actor class consists of hidden local variables, including acquaintance actors to which messages can be sent, plus an interface of *message servers* (*msgsrv*) [24]. A *msgsrv* is a void method which can have arguments. It is devoted to processing an homonymous message. The body of a *msgsrv* is a block of instructions which includes *assignment*, *if-then-else*, *send* and *delay* operations. The instruction *dest.send(msgsrv-name[, args]) [after] [deadline]* sends asynchronously to the *dest* actor a request to execute a given *msgsrv*. The optional *after* and *deadline* time attributes are relative to the sending time and, respectively, specify that the

message cannot be delivered before *after* time units are elapsed, and that, would time go beyond the *deadline*, the message loses its validity and needs to be discarded. The default values for *after* and *deadline* are, respectively, 0 and ∞ . The duration of a *msgsrv* can be specified through a *delay(d)* operation. If used, delay must be the last operation of a *msgsrv*.

The semantics of a Theatre model [11] can be formally specified as a timed transition system in which each state is composed of (a) the current value of the global time (*now*), (b) the union of all the actor data statuses, (c) the bag of the already sent but not yet dispatched messages, (d) the bag of the already set but not yet expired delays. Two types of transitions exist: (i) a *time transition* which advances the global time to the occurrence time of the most imminent event (message dispatch or delay expiration), (ii) an *action transition* which specifies either the execution of a message server (message dispatch) or a delay expiration (which makes free a given PU). If multiple events occur at the same time, one of them is chosen not-deterministically.

In [11], it is shown how a Theatre model naturally can be reduced to UPPAAL for model checking. A given model [16] can be transitioned without distortions down to design, prototyping and implementation phases [15,16,25] with a good degree of compliance and faithfulness [32].

4.2. Introducing Hybrid Actors

The basic version of Theatre is extended so as to be more apt for CPSs. CPSs need, during analysis, a proper modelling of the continuous behaviour of the external environment of the physical part, to be integrated with the (event and time) discrete behaviour of the cyber part. For this reason, the notion of *continuous mode* was added by following the concepts of hybrid automata [12,33]. Differently from [12], continuous modes are considered as independent components which are modelled externally to the application actors, and that naturally can execute in parallel.

A continuous mode is activated by an actor (called *accessor* in [34]). An activation consists of (a) an *initialization*, (b) an *invariant*, (c) one or more *flows*, (d) a *guard*, and (e) a final *action*. The final action reduces to a message send in Hybrid Theatre, which triggers a response in the accessor actor. The flows are used to capture the dynamical laws (expressed through ordinary differential equations) regulating the continuous behaviour of some environmental variables. A mode can be mapped onto UPPAAL Statistical Model Checker (UPPAAL SMC) [17,18] so as to enable a thorough analysis of a Hybrid Theatre model. Continuous modes can be kept in the final synthesis of a model, as *interface components* which access the (naturally changing) environment through a mediator component (see the *envGateway* in [16]). Another refinement was added to Hybrid Theatre for augmenting the compliance of an analysed model with its implementation [25], and also for improving modeller activity by guaranteeing that the messages having the same time (i.e., simultaneous messages) and which are sent, for instance, by a source actor to a same destination actor, instead of being handled not-deterministically, are delivered in the sending order. For this reason, a Lamport logical clock [35] was purposely added to messages as an ordering attribute. By using this newly added attribute, messages are delivered according to their (absolutised) *after* times, but, in the case multiple messages have the same occurrence time, their actual delivery order is determined according to their Lamport logical clocks.

4.3. Cross-Model Aspects When Modelling with Hybrid Theatre

In order to reduce a Hybrid Theatre model onto UPPAAL SMC, it is required to preliminarily define some information like the unique IDs for actors, delays, message names, message instances, and modes, together with suitable type ranges to control the creation of corresponding automata instances. Dynamism of message exchanges is ensured by anticipating a *pool* of message instances (see the *avM[.]* array in Figure 3). The *send[.]* channel gets a message instance ID through the *nM()* function, which returns the first available instance in the message pool. In the case the pool is under-dimensioned, an error arises during the operations of the model checker. When sending a message (see, e.g.,

5. The UPPAAL Model for the Home Energy Management System

The HEMS was firstly developed by using Actors and the Theatre architecture and subsequently reduced to UPPAAL timed automata by exploiting the approach described in [11]. For this reason, in the following, the terms “UPPAAL model” and “actor model” are interchangeable and express the same entity. The approach has been extended so as to take into account continuous modes. This section proposes the UPPAAL models for the Controller, the EMeter, the EHVAC actor and those of all the other enhanced loads described in Section 3. Besides the EHVAC actor model, all the other load actors are modelled by using the same UPPAAL template named *Tabular Load* template. This is because the consumption curves of all the appliances, except the HVAC, evolves as piece-wise constant functions (see Figure 2) and the *Tabular Load* is a configurable template whose behaviour evolves according to this kind of functions which are achieved through a tabular representation of distinct pairs $\langle \text{constant_value}; \text{duration} \rangle$. The Controller and the Meter, instead, do not make use of continuous modes. For simplicity, the template of the Load Manager is not shown since it only carries out the initialization phase of the system.

5.1. The UPPAAL Model for the Tabular Load Actors

The model (see Figure 4) evolves according the three phases (i.e., coasting forward, prediction, active) described in Section 3. The communication between a tabular load and the controller relies on message exchange. The same holds for the communication originating from the mode of the tabular load and directed to the load itself. Communication from the load toward the mode is instead achieved by using the broadcast urgent channels `deactivate[.]`, `activate[.]`, and `predict[.]`, which, respectively, are used to: deactivating and freezing out a mode (if active), and to start the coasting forward; resuming mode execution or making the mode active for the first time; starting the prediction phase. A load, after the INIT message, receives the ON message, thus starting the interactions with the controller by issuing a REQUEST for its admission. On receiving the COASTINGF message, the load deactivates its mode and stays at rest until the coasting forward completes and it receives a READYTOPREDICT coming from its mode. This message is then forwarded to the controller, which will reply with a PREDICT as soon as the prediction phase can start. At the end of the prediction phase, the mode sends a PREDICTIONEND to the load which, in turn, first sends this message to the controller and then waits for receiving an ACTIVATE. After being activated, the load receives a SAMPLE message each time the own mode completes the execution of the current constant piece of the power curve, i.e., the current $\langle \text{constant_value}; \text{duration} \rangle$ pair. The TERMINATED message is received by the load when the mode completes its whole behaviour. This message is then sent to the controller to inform that the load is no longer active.

The mode of a tabular load is portrayed in Figure 5. It provides both the real and the predicted consumption curve of a load. In order to furnish the sampled values of these curves, the mode uses, respectively, the functions `getRealPower(.)` and `getPredictedPower(.)`. The mode samples the consumption curve every PERIOD time units. Two clocks are exploited, namely `time`, for the real consumption curve, and `timeM`, for the predicted one. According to these clocks, the functions `decrementNormalTime(. , .)` and `decrementMirrorTime(. , .)` are used to go ahead, respectively, in the tables containing the tabular values of the real and the predicted power curves. The initial location of the automata is `Idle`, and the mode returns again in this location as it completes to provide the whole real consumption curve. A synchronization with the `activate[.]` broadcast urgent channel moves the automaton in the `Hold` location in which the real consumption curve of the load is sampled and provided. A synchronization with the `deactivate[.]` broadcast urgent channel leads the mode into the `Wait` location in which the two clocks are frozen (see the invariant $\text{time}' == 0 \ \&\& \ \text{timeM}' == 0$) and the mode becomes ready to start the prediction. The `CoastingForward` location is used for coasting forward, here `timeM` increases up to reach the value of the frozen `time` clock (see the invariant $\text{timeM} \leq \text{timeLimit} \ \&\& \ \text{time}' == 0$, where `timeLimit` is set to the frozen value of `time`).

A synchronization with the `predict[.]` broadcast urgent channel moves the mode into the `Predict` location in which the predicted consumption curve is sampled and provided. Here, only the clock `time` is frozen, whereas `timeM` grows up to reach the `PERIOD` value (see the invariant $time' == 0 \wedge timeM \leq PERIOD$). When the prediction completes, the mode moves back into the `Hold` location by following an activation, or into `CoastingForward` by following another deactivation.

Figure 5. The Mode for the Load actor model.

5.2. The UPPAAL Model for the HVAC actor

The following describes the actor model of the HVAC inverter heat pump considered as one appliance in the HEMS model. As emerges from Figure 2d, the power curve actually lasts about 110 time units, and it is given by the composition of four different continuous functions. As a consequence, four different modes, namely $M1$, $M2$, $M3$ and $M4$, are required for generating, respectively, the four sub-curves. The mode $M2$ and $M4$ keep the power to a constant value, whereas $M1$ and $M3$ have, respectively, the following dynamic law $p' = K1 * (h - p)$ and $p' = -K2 * p$, where p is the power function, p' is its first derivative, and $K1$, $K2$ and h are constants (i.e., $K1 = 0.04$, $K2 = 0.3$ and $h = 10.0$). The modes so far described are responsible for the behaviour of the actor when it is active. Further mirror modes, namely, respectively, $M1Mirror$, $M2Mirror$, $M3Mirror$ and $M4Mirror$, are introduced to provide the actor behaviour during the coasting forward and the prediction phases.

Figure 6a shows the $M1$ mode. Initially, the mode finds itself in the `Idle` location. By following instead a synchronization on the urgent broadcast channel `activate[self]`, it

moves to the *Hold* location in which the power function p varies according to the dynamic law of the normal mode and the clock t , which models the time of the mode, evolves too. Despite the current location, instead, by following a synchronization on the urgent broadcast channel `deactivate[self]` the mode reaches, without time passage, the *Pause* location in which the power function and the time are frozen (i.e., $t' == 0 \&\& p' == 0$). Just before reaching such a location, the mode activates its mirror counterpart through a synchronization on the urgent broadcast channel `activate[M1M]`. The mode $M1$ stays in the location *Hold* as long as the invariant condition $t \leq T1$ holds. Exiting from this location, the mode completes its behaviour reaching the *End* location and subsequently returns back to the *Idle* location sending a `SAMPLE` message to the HVAC actor. The other modes have a behaviour very close to that of $M1$ and, for this reason, are not described.

Figure 6. A normal mode and a mirror mode of the HVAC actor.

The *M1Mirror* mode is shown in Figure 6b. The initial location of the mode is *Idle*. By following a synchronization on the urgent broadcast channel `activate[self]` it reaches the *CoastingForward* location. Here, the predicted power function pm starts to grow according to the same law of the power function of its corresponding normal mode $M1$. The coasting forward terminates as soon as the clock of the mirror mode tm reaches the same time reached by the normal mode $M1$. All of this is purposely expressed by the invariant $tm \leq timeLimit \&\& pm' \leq K1 * (h - pm)$. The variable *timeLimit* is initialized on the arc outgoing the *Idle* location. On exiting the *CoastingForward* location, the mirror mode sends a `READYTOPREDICT` message to the HVAC actor and enters the *Wait* location. The mode remains here until it synchronizes with the urgent broadcast channel `predict[self]` and moves to the *Predict* location. Here, the predicted power evolves by following the same law of the real power of the mode $M1$. At the end of the prediction, the current mirror mode notifies the next mirror mode of the HVAC which, in this case, is the *M2Mirror* mode. It is worth noting that, once the prediction phase is started within a mirror mode, the next one has to continue this phase without executing the coasting forward. This is mirrored by the fact that *M1Mirror* exits from the *Predict* location by synchronizing with the broadcast urgent channel `predict[M2M]`. The other mirror modes have a behaviour similar to that of *M1Mirror* and, for this reason, are not reported. The only substantial difference is that the other mirror modes are required to hear a further synchronization when staying in the *Idle* location which permits them to start the mode

behaviour by directly going into the Predict location, thus bypassing the coasting forward. The last mirror mode, i.e., the *M4Mirror* mode, on exiting the Predict location will send a message to the HVAC informing that the prediction phase is completed.

The model for the HVAC is reported in Figure 7. When active, the HVAC actor behaves as a finite state machine whose current state is defined by the current mode (*cm*). On receiving the ON message, the HVAC sets the first mode as its current mode, i.e., *cm* = *M1*, and sends to the controller a request for activation. In the same way as for the tabular loads, by interacting with the controller, the HVAC moves first into the coasting forward phase, then into prediction and, finally, into the active phase. This last phase is triggered by receiving an ACTIVATE message. When the current mode terminates, i.e., a SAMPLE message is received, and then the next mode is activated. The behaviour of the appliance completes when the last mode, namely the *M4* one, terminates. As described in Section 3, the controller can stop the active phase and move again the HVAC into the coasting forward phase, each time a new load asks for its admission. Other details of the HVAC model should be self-explanatory.

Figure 7. The HVAC actor model.

5.3. The UPPAAL Model for the Controller Actor

The Controller actor (see Figure 8) periodically receives POWER messages from the meter. One of such messages has two arguments carrying out information about the current power consumption, both real and predicted, of the whole system. Since all the loads stay simultaneously in the active or prediction phase (see Section 3), the two arguments cannot be at the same time greater than zero. The measured predicted power consumption will be greater than zero only if a new load sends a REQUEST and the HEMS switches in prediction. During prediction, in the case the predicted power is found to be greater than the consumption threshold, the variable `inadmissibleLoad` is set to `true`, indicating that the new load cannot be served at this moment. In such a case, the current request is deferred by `DELAYTIME` time units. In no case, the real power consumption of the system can exceed the threshold. In order to check this condition, the invariant $realPW \leq threshold$ is set for the location E of the controller automaton. On receiving a REQUEST message, the controller evolves according to the schema described in the following:

1. the controller sends to each active load (if any) the COASTINGF message;
2. as soon as all the loads replied with a READYTOPREDICT, the controller sends them a PREDICT message;
3. when all the loads replied with a PREDICTIONEND, the controller checks the value of the `inadmissibleLoad` variable, thus deciding to admit or defer the new load. In the former case, an ACTIVATE message is sent to the new load;
4. an ACTIVATE message is sent to each previously active loads.

Figure 8. The UPPAAL model of the controller.

In the case multiple REQUESTs arrive to the controller, only the first one is considered, while the others are deferred by `DELAYTIME` time units. Besides the entities so far described, the controller operates by using the variables and the functions reported in Table 2. Each array in the table has a length equal to the number of loads existing in the system. Other details of the controller should be self-explanatory.

Table 2. Variables and functions exploited by the Controller actor.

Identifier	Type	Description
isOn	boolean array	an element is true if the corresponding load was admitted by the controller
nextON	function	iterates on the array of admitted loads
inPrediction	integer var	number of loads which are in prediction
inCoastingForward	integer var	number of loads which are in coasting forward
isCoastingForward	boolean array	an element is true if the corresponding load is in coasting forward
toAdmit	integer var	the load that asked for admission
isActive	boolean array	an element is true if the corresponding load is active
termination	boolean array	indicates whether a load has completed its execution

5.4. The UPPAAL Model for the Meter Actor

The meter (see Figure 9a) has a periodic behaviour, which in turn depends on the *Clock* actor (see Figure 9b), which sends a *TICK* message to the meter after each *PERIOD* time unit. The meter reacts to a *TICK* by sending a *POWER* message to the controller together with the current value of the total load power consumption, both real and predicted, obtained by invoking, respectively, the *realPower()* and the *predictedPower()* function. In such a way, the sampling frequency of the HEMS is defined by the *PERIOD* value. Changing only this value, thought, is not enough to evaluate how the point-of-view of the controller changes with respect to the actual value of the real and predicted power consumption curves. In order to achieve this, it is required that the meter samples the consumption curves with a given sample but only a subset of these samples are then sent to the meter. A *SCALE* integer factor is introduced, and the behaviour of the meter automaton is slightly modified so as to sent the power messages to the controller every *SCALE* times. As a consequence, the sampling time of the controller is given by $SCALE * PERIOD$, but the sampling time with which the power curves are sampled by the meter remains to be *PERIOD*.

Figure 9. The Meter (a) and the Clock (b) actor.

6. Property Checking and Experimental Results

The goal of the analysis phase is two-fold. First, it is devoted to checking if the controller is able to properly behave, i.e., if the prediction policy is able to prevent the overcoming of the threshold during system operation. Second, it is devoted to checking the proper coupling between the cyber and the physical part of the system, i.e., to check if the cyber part of the HEMS is able to correctly interact with the physical part given a specific value of the sampling frequency. As described in Section 5.4, the sampling period of the meter is determined by *PERIOD*, whereas the period with which the controller receives information about the consumption curves is given by $SCALE \times PERIOD$. In what follows, *PERIOD* is set to 0.1. This value was chosen experimentally by checking that a smaller value for the period did not affect the resolution of the observed consumption curves.

The behaviour of the HEMS reduced to UPPAAL SMC was checked in two cases: (a) the control strategy is not required, i.e., a threshold value is set which permits the contemporary admission of all the loads in the system at the same time; and (b) the control policy is required to prevent the overcome of the threshold. While executing the experiments, in no case, the invariant $realPW \leq threshold$ (see Section 5.3) of the controller was violated. All the experiments refer to the critical case in which all the loads immediately ask for their admission to the controller.

A first set of Metric Interval Temporal Logic (MITL) queries [18] were issued with a threshold set to 7, a SCALE set to 1, and a DELAYTIME set to 1. For each result, where applicable, are reported the number of runs requested by the Uppaal SMC to get the result and the confidence interval of the result with a confidence level of 0.95.

Q1: $Pr[\leq 2000](\langle \rangle predictedPower() > threshold)$

Q2: $Pr[\leq 2000](\langle \rangle realPower() > threshold)$

R1–R2: (29 runs) $Pr(\langle \rangle \dots)$ in $[0, 0.0981446]$ with confidence 0.95.

Q3: $simulate[\leq 700]\{ realPower(), -predictedPower(), threshold, -numActiveLoads() \}$

R3: The picture in Figure 10.

Q4: $Pr[\leq 700]([\] (Hvac(HV).msgCounter==1 \ \&\& \ Hvac(HV).msg==ON) \ | \ | \ (Hvac(HV).msgCounter!=1) \)$

Q5: $Pr[\leq 700]([\] (Hvac(HV).msgCounter==2 \ \&\& \ Hvac(HV).msg==COASTINGF) \ | \ | \ (Hvac(HV).msgCounter!=2) \)$

Q6: $Pr[\leq 700]([\] (Hvac(HV).msgCounter==3 \ \&\& \ Hvac(HV).msg==READYTOPREDICT) \ | \ | \ (Hvac(HV).msgCounter!=3) \)$

Q7: $Pr[\leq 700]([\] (Hvac(HV).msgCounter==4 \ \&\& \ Hvac(HV).msg==PREDICT) \ | \ | \ (Hvac(HV).msgCounter!=4) \)$

Q8: $Pr[\leq 700]([\] (Hvac(HV).msgCounter==5 \ \&\& \ Hvac(HV).msg==PREDICTIONEND) \ | \ | \ (Hvac(HV).msgCounter!=5) \)$

Q9: $Pr[\leq 700]([\] (Hvac(HV).msgCounter==6 \ \&\& \ Hvac(HV).msg==ACTIVATE) \ | \ | \ (Hvac(HV).msgCounter!=6) \)$

R4–R9: (29 runs) $Pr([\] \dots)$ in $[0.901855, 1]$ with confidence 0.95.

Queries Q1 and Q2 are devoted to check, within a time interval of 2000 time units, the probability to find, respectively, the predicted power and the real power greater than the threshold. The results R1 and R2 indicate that these events are practically impossible as they have $[0, 0.0981446]$ as confidence interval.

The query Q3 asks the Uppaal SMC verifier to simulate, in a time interval of 700 time units, the evolution of: the real power consumption, the predicted power, and the number of active loads. From the simulation outcomes, it is possible to see how the HEMS evolves and how the controller evaluates the cumulative predicted power consumption curve as soon as new loads ask for their admission. When the controller has considered the cumulative prediction curves of all the loads, all the loads are switched into active.

The queries from Q4 to Q9 checks if the HVAC receives the control messages in the right order. By considering the query results from R1 to R9, it is possible to state that the HEMS behaves properly.

A further set of queries were issued to check the correctness of the HEMS in the case the controller has to defer the admission of some loads in order to meet the threshold. In this second scenario, a threshold set to 5 and the DELAYTIME set to 15 were considered. SCALE and PERIOD have remained unchanged.

Q10: $Pr[\leq 1700](\langle \rangle realPower() > threshold)$

R10: (29 runs) $Pr(\langle \rangle \dots)$ in $[0, 0.0981446]$ with confidence 0.95.

Q11: $Pr[\leq 1700](\langle \rangle predictedPower() > threshold)$

R11: (29 runs) $Pr(\langle \rangle \dots)$ in $[0.901855, 1]$ with confidence 0.95.

Q12: $Pr[\leq 2000]([] \text{ now} < 1999 \mid \mid \text{ forall}(i : \text{int}[0, \text{TABLOADS} + \text{ODELOADS} - 1]) \text{ termination}[i] == \text{true})$

R12: (29 runs) $Pr([] \dots)$ in $[0.901855, 1]$ with confidence 0.95.

Q13: $\text{simulate} [\leq 1700] \{ \text{realPower}(), -\text{predictedPower}(), \text{threshold}, -\text{numActiveLoads}() \}$

R13: The picture in Figure 11.

Figure 10. The real and predicted power consumption (in KW) and the number of active loads during load scheduling with a threshold of 7 (KW).

The query $Q10$ checks the probability of finding the real power greater than the threshold. Furthermore, in this case, $R10$ states that this event is practically impossible. The query $Q11$ instead checks the probability to have the predicted power consumption greater than the threshold. In such a case, instead, the probability of this event is very high, and it can be considered as practically certain. The query $Q12$ checks the probability to have all the loads terminated at the 2000th time instant. $R12$ confirms that such an event is practically certain. By considering $R10$, $R11$ and $R12$, it is possible to conclude that the exploited admission control policy is really effective in managing the activation scheduling of the loads. Query $Q13$ is devoted to showing a simulation tied to the evolution of the HEMS in terms of real power, predicted power and number of active loads.

In order to assess how a change in the sampling frequency of the controller affects its ability to control the load scheduling, two other scenarios were considered by varying the value of the $SCALE$ variable. More in detail, by setting $SCALE$ to 100, from Figure 12a it follows that the controller is not able to correctly schedule the loads. In fact, the real power consumption overcame the threshold during load activation. This is also witnessed by $R14$, where it emerges that the probability to have the real power over the threshold has a confidence interval of $[0.893009, 0.992099]$. A more subtle case is that concerning the $SCALE$ set to 10. In this case, a single simulation is not able to highlight any point in which the real power overcomes the threshold (see Figure 12b). A deeper analysis carried out by using the statistical model checker shows instead that, by considering 364 runs, the probability to have a threshold violation has a confidence interval of $[0.29207, 0.391866]$. In other words, with a $SCALE$ set to 10, the controller is not able to properly behave.

Q14: $Pr[\leq 1000](\langle \rangle realPower() > threshold)$

R14: (79 runs) $Pr(\langle \rangle \dots)$ in $[0.893009, 0.992099]$ with confidence 0.95.

Q15: $Pr[\leq 1000](\langle \rangle realPower() > threshold)$

R15: (364 runs) $Pr(\langle \rangle \dots)$ in $[0.29207, 0.391866]$ with confidence 0.95.

Figure 11. The real power and predicted power consumption (in KW) and number of active loads during load scheduling with a threshold of 5 (KW).

Figure 12. The consumption curve (in KW) of the considered appliances vs. time in the case two different SCALE factors are used.

7. Conclusions

This paper proposed an approach exploitable for developing Home Energy Management Systems (HEMSs). The approach leverages hybrid actors [12], the Theatre infrastruc-

ture [11], and model continuity [16]. The assessment of the system properties was achieved by preliminarily reducing the Theatre model onto the UPPAAL hybrid timed automata and subsequently by using the statistical model checker.

The considered HEMS case study was chosen for highlighting the effectiveness and usability of the approach. The goal of the case study was two-folds: (i) evaluating how the setting of a given sampling frequency affects the behaviour of the whole HEMS; (ii) experimenting with an admission control policy able to prevent an overload upfront by predicting the effect that the admission of a new load will have on the consumption curve of the whole system. Ongoing and future work is geared at:

- Extending the case study by considering more complex scheduling policies and by using a more general deterministic version of Theatre actors;
- Completing the development of the proposed HEMS with preliminary and final system implementation;
- Enhancing the capabilities of the *envGateway* by offering basic design constructs and mechanisms for simplifying modelling and analysis of more complex physical environments;
- Experimenting with the proposed approach in more-general IoT-based applications, e.g., in augmented environments like smart homes and smart offices;
- Investigating the possibility of exhaustive model checking a Hybrid Theatre model, by following an approach similar to that adopted in Hybrid Rebeca [12].

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